

D7.1

Action Plan Methodology

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Abbreviations

AP	Action Plan
BAU	Business as Usual
DGs	Directorates-General
GVA	Gross Value Added
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TWG	Thematic Working Groups

Introduction to the project

BOOST4BIOEAST is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the European Commission developed to support the BIOEAST Initiative with the aim of empowering national stakeholders in the Central Eastern European and Baltic countries for the development of national bioeconomy action plans and to build long-lasting structures and spaces of dialogue for national and macro-regional cooperation. The project will enrich knowledge on the bioeconomy and stimulate related research and innovation across the macro-region.

Executive Summary

The BOOST4BIOEAST action planning process is a collaborative, future-oriented approach designed to empower stakeholders and policymakers in Central Eastern European and Baltic countries to develop effective national bioeconomy Action Plans (APs). This report details the methodology of the process, which centers around a three-day workshop where participants engage in diagnosis (system mapping and SWOT analysis), and vision building to co-create actionable plans for bioeconomy development. The process emphasises adaptability and future-proofing, ensuring that the plans can withstand potential disruptions and align with the broader EU Bioeconomy Strategy (EC 2018; Roney 2010). By fostering collaboration and strategic thinking, this methodology aims to drive transformative change and pave the way for a sustainable and prosperous bioeconomy in the BIOEAST region.

1 Introduction

The BOOST4BIOEAST action planning process aims to collaboratively develop and future-proof national bioeconomy APs by engaging stakeholders and policymakers through innovative approaches. It seeks to bridge the gap between national strategies and APs, providing a versatile framework for organisations to strategise effectively. By stress-testing these plans against plausible EU-level scenarios, the process enhances their adaptability and strengthens the Futures Literacy¹ of participants (Miller 2015; Toni *et al.* 2015). Ultimately, it empowers decision-makers, experts, and stakeholders with analytical skills and foresight, enabling them to co-create APs that outline a desirable 2040 vision for bioeconomy development, define goals for key stakeholders, and recommend concrete short-, medium-, and long-term actions to achieve these goals.

This document contains the methodology for developing bioeconomy APs, which is based on the Three Horizons approach (Sharpe *et al.* 2016; Tsoukas *et al.* 2004). This methodology, described in detail in Chapter 2, will be implemented through a three-day workshop that will be organised and facilitated by HUB Coordinators in each BIOEAST country. The workshop will bring together stakeholders from different sectors of the bioeconomy to co-create national APs. The workshop is designed to be highly interactive and participatory and will use a variety of tools and techniques to engage participants.

Chapter 3 ensures that HUB Coordinators are fully equipped with the current knowledge on the status of national bioeconomies by explaining how to conduct the bioeconomy system

¹ Futures literacy is the capability to understand the future as a space for diverse possibilities and to use the future to guide present-day decisions and actions (Miller 2015; Toni *et al.* 2015)

mapping and contextual analysis exercises prior to the workshops. Chapter 4 provides a full breakdown of the three-day workshop with guidance on effective facilitation.

Chapter 5 describes in detail the first day of the workshop which focuses on mapping and visualizing the bioeconomy ecosystem where participants will identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges within the bioeconomy system. This will allow them to create the business as usual (BAU) vision for 2040.

Chapter 6 outlines the second day dedicated to formulating a desirable vision for the bioeconomy and identifying gaps between the BAU vision and the desirable vision where participants will design actions for implementation to realize the desirable vision for the bioeconomy.

Chapter 7 focuses on the third day that will be used to future-proof the APs. The content of the APs will be tested from the perspective of different possible futures. This will allow participants to amend the APs, making them resistant to potential future disruptions.

This methodology aims to provide guidance for the HUBs in order to maintain consistency across BIOEAST countries in the development of the APs, but it is at the same time flexible and can be adapted to the specific needs of each country.

2 Guiding approach for action planning: the Three Horizons Method

When considering the future, we often fall into the trap of assuming current trends will simply continue. However, the reality is that our world is complex, dynamic, and full of uncertainties. Unexpected events, like the COVID pandemic or cyberattacks, can drastically alter the course of trends, either accelerating or disrupting them entirely. This highlights the need for foresight, a process that acknowledges the unpredictable nature of the future and recognizes that we have the power to influence its trajectory.

Foresight rests on three core principles: firstly, the future is not predetermined; there's a vast array of potential outcomes. Secondly, while we cannot predict the future, we can explore plausible scenarios and assess their likelihood. Lastly, our present choices can shape the future, increasing the probability of desired outcomes (Sacio-Szymańska & Nosarzewski 2019; Kuosa 2011).

It's important to note that strategic foresight is not a replacement for traditional planning and decision-making, but rather a tool to enhance these processes. It provides valuable insights into potential opportunities and challenges, leading to more robust and future-proof strategies. Ultimately, strategic foresight is for any actor, public or private, who seeks to navigate the

complexities of the future and proactively shape their destiny (Bootz 2010; Minkkinen 2020; Rohrbeck & Schwarz 2013).

The Three Horizons methodology (Sharpe *et al.* 2016; Tsoukas & Shepherd 2004) is a framework encouraging to explore the future through the lens of three distinct phases, each representing a different timeframe and perspective:

Horizon 1: Diagnosis

This horizon represents the present state of the bioeconomy, encompassing existing systems, technologies, and practices. It's about understanding the current landscape, identifying strengths and weaknesses, and acknowledging the trends that are shaping the near future.

Horizon 2: Visioning

This horizon involves projecting both BAU and desirable bioeconomy visions to encompass possible futures and guide us toward the optimal one.

- BAU vision is a projection of how the bioeconomy system will evolve if no significant interventions or changes occur.
- Desirable Vision is a projection of the preferable future state of the bioeconomy system. By articulating a clear and compelling vision, we can set a direction for our actions and inspire stakeholders to work towards a common goal.

Horizon 3: Strategising

This horizon represents the "bridge" between the BAU and the desirable vision. It's about identifying the gap between the current trajectory and the desired future state and developing strategies to close that gap. This involves identifying key interventions, innovations, and policy changes needed to transition towards the desirable vision.

By exploring these three horizons, HUBs can develop a more comprehensive understanding of the future and its potential implications for the bioeconomy. This allows the HUBs to craft APs that are not only relevant to the present but also adaptable to the challenges and opportunities of the future.

3 Prior to workshop preparations

3.1 Mapping current landscape and dynamics within each country's bioeconomy system - preliminary analysis

HUB Coordinators fill a standardised template (Appendix 1) to gather comprehensive information on the key elements of the bioeconomy system within their respective BIOEAST countries. This template guides them to systematically analyse and document crucial aspects

across various bioeconomy sectors (agriculture, forestry, fisheries, aquaculture, organic waste management, food production, wood and paper industries, biochemicals, biomaterials, bioenergy, bio-based services and other specific sectors relevant to their country). Information is then grouped according to the following BIOEAST Thematic Working Groups (TWG) themes:

- Agroecology and sustainable yields,
- Biobased materials,
- Bioenergy & new value-added materials,
- Bioeconomy education,
- Food systems,
- Forest value chain,
- Freshwater-based bioeconomy.

Linking to the TWG's areas of focus will help leverage the outcomes of the thematic groups' work and enabling better alignment with their findings. The workshop insights can be also used by the TWGs as a starting point for the thematic Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) development and other future discussions.

The collected data and also the BIOEAST countries' concept papers (https://bioeast.eu/knowledge-platform/?_search=concept%20paper) prepared as a part of the BIOEASTsUP (<https://bioeast.eu/bioeastsup/>) Horizon 2020 EU project in 2023 serves as a valuable foundation for understanding the current landscape and dynamics within each country's bioeconomy.

3.2 Bioeconomy system mapping - synthesising the information

Before the workshops, HUB Coordinators prepare a first draft of the system map for bioeconomy in the specific country, based on the data from templates and countries' concept papers. Maps are organised according to the themes:

- Agroecology and sustainable yields,
- Biobased materials,
- Bioenergy & new value-added materials,
- Bioeconomy education,
- Food systems,
- Forest value chain,
- Freshwater-based bioeconomy.

Not all HUBs will focus on all 7 themes but will work on the ones of national priority laid down in their Terms of Reference document. The optimum and suggested number of themes to work with during the workshop is up to 5.

3.3 Introduction to the contextual analysis of the bioeconomy system

3.3.1 Survey for the workshop participants and other sources of information

To streamline the workshop process and ensure a smooth flow, HUB Coordinators have the option to run a survey and utilise its responses to pre-populate the results of Exercise 3 (see the Overview of the workshops chapter below). This allows for efficient verification and validation of the identified strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges during the workshop itself, saving valuable time and enabling more in-depth discussions and analysis. Appendix 2 contains the survey template.

The survey asks participants to identify five strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges within the bioeconomy system, focusing on the themes that will be explored during the workshop. The outputs of the SWOT analysis in the national concept papers prepared during BIOEASTsUP (if available) can also be validated during Exercise 3.

This pre-workshop reflection will enable deeper discussions and help participants develop a well-considered vision of the future in the BAU scenario (see sub-section 5.2.4 below).

4 Overview of the workshops

Three days of workshops will be organised and facilitated in national languages or in English by the HUB Coordinators in each BIOEAST HUB between M13 and M30 in order to co-design the national bioeconomy APs with HUB members. The workshops are designed to be organised online, but they can be online or in-person, depending on the HUB's need and budget. The overview of the workshops is shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Three-day workshop to develop a bioeconomy AP with draft agenda

Day 1. Diagnosis & Visioning	Time needed
Exercise 1: System mapping - further investigation	1 h and 15 minutes
Exercise 2: Report-back in plenary - validation of bioeconomy system map	30 min
Exercise 3: Contextual analysis of the bioeconomy system	2,5 h
Exercise 4: Developing a 2040 BAU vision of the bioeconomy system	1 h
Summary, feedback and closure	20 minutes
Day 2. Visioning & Strategizing	
Exercise 5: Formulating desirable vision for the bioeconomy	40 minutes
Exercise 6: Report-back - Ensuring alignment and cohesion among desirable vision elements	30 minutes

Exercise 7: Area-specific strategic planning	3 h
Exercise 8: Report-back - Strategising for the bioeconomy considered holistically	1 h
Summary, feedback and closure	20 minutes
Day 3. Future-proofing	
Exercise 9: Scenario analysis	1 h
Exercise 10: Future-proofing	2,5 h
Exercise 11: Report back	1 h
Summary, feedback and closure	20 minutes

It is important to note that **there will be an additional stage between the initial two-day workshop (Days 1-2) and the Future-Proofing workshop (Day 3). This stage involves aligning the SRIA and the APs.** Therefore, HUB Coordinators should plan for a 4-5 month gap between Day 2 and Day 3 to accommodate the SRIA and APs alignment process.

The success of the workshops hinges on the active participation of diverse stakeholders. By including representatives from various areas such as government, industry, academia, and civil society, the workshops can tap into a broader pool of knowledge and perspectives. This diversity fosters a more nuanced understanding of the complexities and interdependencies within the bioeconomy system. Furthermore, it encourages collaboration and knowledge-sharing among different actors, paving the way for the co-creation of innovative and inclusive APs.

The optimum number of participants is from 20 to 30.

To ensure a diverse and balanced representation of perspectives in each group, participants can be distributed as follows:

- Policy & Governance: 5-6 participants
- Research & Innovation: 5-6 participants
- Business & Industry: 5-6 participants
- Civil Society & NGOs: 5-6 participants

Consider participants' specific knowledge and experience when assigning them to groups focused on different value chain categories (production, processing, consumption, recycling & pre-production).

Effective facilitation and organisation are crucial for successful workshops. To ensure smooth and productive sessions, the following roles and resources are recommended:

- Master Facilitator (1): a skilled facilitator with experience in guiding group discussions, managing time effectively, and ensuring that the workshop objectives are met. The

Master Facilitator will oversee the overall flow of the workshop and provide support to the group facilitators. It is highly recommended that HUB Coordinators take the role of the Master Facilitator.

- Group Facilitators (4-5, depending on the number of thematic groups): experienced facilitators assigned to each thematic group. They will guide discussions within their respective groups, encourage participation, and ensure that all perspectives are heard. These facilitators can also serve as notetakers, capturing key insights and discussion points for use in developing the final AP.
- Organizational Person (1): responsible for logistical arrangements, including venue booking (if in-person), material preparation, or technical support (if online). This role ensures a smooth and well-organised workshop environment.

5 Workshop design - Day 1: Diagnosis & Visioning

5.1 Overall objectives

- Mapping and visualising a bioeconomy ecosystem.
- Identifying strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges regarding the development of a bioeconomy ecosystem divided into themes and sub-themes.
- Creating the vision of the future in its BAU form, that is if the actual trends (both positive and negative) continue.

5.2 Exercises

5.2.1 Exercise 1: System mapping - further investigation

The objective of this part of the workshop is to develop a comprehensive system map of bioeconomy in the country, including biomass resources, value chains, stakeholders, biorefineries, and their interrelationships. This will provide a clear and concise visualisation of the bioeconomy landscape. The system map will be directly incorporated into the AP (reporting template for the AP is in the Appendix 3).

It's a group work consisting of the following steps:

Ex. 1. Step 1. Introduction (10 min)

The HUB Coordinator outlines the objectives, methodology, and desired outcomes. Participants gain a clear understanding of the workshop process and its significance in the whole process of preparing the AP.

Ex. 1. Step 2. Presentation of the bioeconomy system (30 min)

The HUB Coordinator is presenting the idea of the system map and its elements. The map is going to be divided into themes specific to the HUB's need chosen from:

- Agroecology and sustainable yields,
- Biobased materials,
- Bioenergy & new value-added materials,
- Bioeconomy education,
- Food systems,
- Forest value chain,
- Freshwater-based bioeconomy.

These themes are divided into sub-themes.

Ex. 1. Step 3. Identification of the missing elements (35 min)

Participants are divided into groups each focusing on the part of the map represented by one of the HUB themes.

Groups identify missing elements to the system map, ensuring a comprehensive representation of the bioeconomy landscape. Conversations delve into the core system elements divided into sub-themes and the broader context, encompassing external driving factors and influences.

Below are guiding questions that can boost and broaden discussion on the system map of the bioeconomy in the country. Some of them may be chosen to discuss during the workshop:

- Identify and examine the key bioeconomy sub-themes currently active in the region. Are there any emerging sub-themes missing that show promise for future development? If so, add them.
- Are there any gaps or missing components in the analysed system, namely: stakeholders, value-chains, biomass resources and biorefineries? If so, add them.
- Verify and complete the predominant value chains within the theme.
- Are there bottlenecks or inefficiencies in the supply chain?
- Are there sufficient facilities for biomass processing, storage, and transportation?
- Discuss and assess new technologies and innovations that can enhance biomass conversion and utilisation.
- Do we have greater production capabilities, or do we need to import it?
- Have we comprehensively mapped all the key driving factors influencing our bioeconomy system, or are there any potential blind spots we need to consider?

Any missing elements, if collectively identified as important to the system, are then added to the system map using Miro boards (Appendix 4; alternatively similar software may be used).

5.2.2 Exercise 2: Report-back in plenary - validation of the bioeconomy system map (30 min)

The map fragments, representing the themes explored in the previous task (Agroecology and sustainable yields, Biobased materials, Bioeconomy education, Bioenergy & new value-added

materials, Food systems, Forest value chain and Freshwater based bioeconomy), are presented in plenary to form the complete map. The HUB Coordinator will guide discussion to find the linkages between elements within the bioeconomy system, deepening the understanding of the complex interactions. Participants will be looking for any gap in the system.

5.2.3 Exercise 3: Contextual analysis of the bioeconomy system (2,5 h)

This section's goal is to identify key strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and challenges (SWOT) of the bioeconomy system as a whole (through the lens of individual sub-themes). The results of this analysis inform the development of the BAU vision for 2040, projecting the likely trajectory of each sub-theme if current trends persist. The process involves a structured SWOT analysis, incorporating insights from facilitated group discussions (and optionally from a pre-workshop survey or other additional materials, like analyses from other projects) to achieve consensus on the top 5 items in each SWOT category. The results of SWOT analysis are then being used to construct a BAU vision for each sub-theme, serving as a foundation for subsequent action planning.

Participants are divided into the previously formed groups based on the HUB themes.

Each group analyses the bioeconomy area broken down to sub-themes:

Ex. 3. Step 1. Mapping key strengths and weaknesses

The work at this stage of the exercise can proceed according to two variants, depending on whether the pre-workshop survey was conducted or not.

If a survey was conducted, the group facilitator presents a concise overview of the key findings from the pre-workshop survey for the sub-theme. The group facilitator displays strengths and weaknesses in the Miro boards, each with a list of items generated from the pre-workshop survey. If a survey was not conducted, the facilitator presents the participants with a template in Miro boards, where they can input propositions for strengths and weaknesses. They can do this individually, using sticky notes, or collectively. At this stage, it is important to gather all the propositions that arise, at the same time assessing their dynamics (see the template below). A voting session follows, where participants use Miro dots to vote for the top 5 items within each category.

The group facilitator leads the discussion guiding the group to agree on the final top 5 items for each category. The group facilitator structures the group discussion on the wording of the top 5 items in each category, encouraging suggestions for corrections or clarifications to ensure clarity and conciseness. This step refines the identified elements for future use in the workshop and AP.

Table 2. Template for mapping key strengths and weaknesses

Bioeconomy system main theme	Description of strength or weakness (max. 5)	Type (strength/weakness)	Dynamics (increasing, decreasing, sustained)
Sub-theme 1	Insight	S	Increasing
	Insight	W	Sustained
	Insight	S	Decreasing

Sub-theme 2	Insight	S	Increasing
	Insight	W	Sustained
	Insight	S	Decreasing

Sub-theme 3	Insight	S	Increasing
	Insight	W	Sustained
	Insight	S	Decreasing

...	Insight

Strength: A positive attribute or characteristic of a bioeconomy system’s sub-theme that contributes to its success or effectiveness.

Examples of strengths:

- supportive policies and regulations,
- high farmer awareness,
- strong research base.

Weakness: A negative attribute or characteristic of a bioeconomy system’s sub-theme that hinders its success or effectiveness.

Examples of weaknesses:

- limited market demand for certain diverse crops,
- lack of effective monitoring and evaluation,
- digital divide.

Ex. 3. Step 2. Mapping key challenges and opportunities

Again, the work at this stage of the exercise can proceed according to two variants, depending on whether the pre-workshop survey was conducted or not.

If a survey was conducted, the group facilitator presents a concise overview of the key findings from the pre-workshop survey for the sub-theme. The facilitator then displays opportunities

and challenges on separate Miro boards, each with a list of items generated from the pre-workshop survey. The list will be used as an inspiration for the defining challenges and opportunities. If a survey was not conducted, the facilitator presents the participants with a template in Miro boards, where they can input propositions for opportunities and challenges. They can do this individually, using sticky notes, or collectively. At this stage, it is important to gather all the propositions that arise.

A discussion session follows, where participants name and vote for (optional) those opportunities and challenges (5 maximum), which are the most impactful in the context of the strengths and weaknesses identified in the previous step (in each sub-theme category).

Table 3. Template for mapping key challenges and opportunities

Bioeconomy system main theme	List of challenges in the context of the strengths & weaknesses (max. 5)	List of opportunities in the context of the strengths & weaknesses (max. 5)
Sub-theme 1	Challenge	Opportunity
	Challenge	Opportunity
	Challenge	Opportunity

Sub-theme 2	Challenge	Opportunity
	Challenge	Opportunity
	Challenge	Opportunity

Sub-theme 3	Challenge	Opportunity
	Challenge	Opportunity
	Challenge	Opportunity

...	Challenge	Opportunity

Challenges: External factors favouring the strengthening of strengths and weakening of weaknesses.

Examples of challenges:

- favourable demographic structure,
- increasing funding,
- emerging new pests and diseases,
- high initial investment costs,
- balancing short-term economic considerations with long-term soil health benefits.

Opportunities: External factors exacerbating weaknesses and/or preventing the development of strengths.

Examples of opportunities:

- improvement of nature-based solutions,
- lack of funding,
- unfavourable regulations,
- lack of social acceptance of a solution
- growing awareness of the importance of soil health for sustainable agriculture,
- development of new biocontrol solutions.

5.2.4 Exercise 4: Developing a 2040 BAU vision for bioeconomy system (1h)

In this exercise participants continue to work in the previously formed groups based on the HUB themes.

Ex. 4. Step 1. Formulating BAU vision of the bioeconomy system in 2040

The group develops a BAU vision of their sub-theme in 2040, assuming direct consequences of continued dynamics of the mapped phenomena (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges).

The main guiding question, which will be posed by the group facilitator at this stage is:

- In view of the identified strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges - assuming no major changes in external driving factors and national policies - is the situation in the sub-theme expected to improve, stabilise or deteriorate by 2040?

Table 4. Template for developing BAU vision of the bioeconomy system in 2040

Bioeconomy system main theme	2040 BAU vision (=> sub-theme projections)
Sub-theme 1	In 2040, (sub-theme name) is expected to (projected outcome based on synthesis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges), assuming current dynamics continue.
Sub-theme 2	In 2040, (sub-theme name) is expected to (projected outcome based on synthesis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges), assuming current dynamics continue.
Sub-theme 3	In 2040, (sub-theme name) is expected to (projected outcome based on synthesis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and challenges), assuming current dynamics continue.
...	...

Following the Three Horizons framework, the group facilitator documents the key findings and inputs made to the BAU visions, ensuring they are incorporated into the final workshop outputs and integrated into the AP.

Examples of BAU visions:

- In 2040, commercialisation of research in the field of crop diversification and rotation is at a very low level, assuming current dynamics continue.
- In 2040, the agricultural landscape features widespread adoption of integrated pest and disease management. Bio-based solutions, fueled by continuous advancements in research and innovation, are prevalent. International collaboration ensures effective risk management across borders.

5.2.5 Summary, feedback and closure

The HUB Coordinator invites participants to reflect on the process in plenary and invites them to share some of the lessons learned using the following guiding questions:

- What was the most valuable thing you learned during this workshop?
- What new perspectives or insights did you gain about bioeconomy that you didn't have before?
- How has this workshop influenced your thinking about bioeconomy?

The HUB Coordinator emphasises the importance of the outputs of the workshop for the next phase of the analysis and for the overall AP development and provides a brief overview of the agenda for Day 2, outlining the focus on vision building and strategizing.

The HUB Coordinator thanks participants for their active engagement and contributions.

5.3 Outcomes

During Day 1, the following key outcomes should be achieved:

- Comprehensive system map: A visual representation of the bioeconomy system, capturing key elements and their interrelationships. This will be incorporated into the AP (section 1.1).
- List of key strengths, weaknesses, challenges and opportunities determining the development of the bioeconomy system (which will inform the diagnostic section of the AP).
- BAU Vision of Bioeconomy in 2040 - a projection of the future state of the bioeconomy system if the dynamics of currently observed phenomena remains unchanged.

Overall, Day 1 provides a strong foundation for further work by establishing a comprehensive understanding of the current bioeconomy system and its key dynamics. These outputs will serve as valuable inputs for vision building, and action planning in the following phases of the process.

6 Workshop design - Day 2: Visioning & Strategising

6.1 Overall objectives

- Formulating a desirable vision for the bioeconomy.
- Identifying gaps between the BAU vision and the desirable vision.
- Designing actions whose implementation will lead to the realisation of the desirable vision for HUB focus areas.

6.2 Exercises

6.2.1 Exercise 5: Formulating desirable vision for the bioeconomy (40 min) - group exercise

This exercise builds upon the previously developed BAU vision. Participants, divided into the HUB specific themes:

- Agroecology and sustainable yields,
- Biobased materials,
- Bioeconomy education,
- Bioenergy & new value-added materials,
- Food systems,
- Forest value chain,
- Freshwater based bioeconomy,

and collaboratively craft a desirable vision for the bioeconomy.

Using a structured template (see Table 5), each group navigates through predefined categories, referencing the sub-themes identified on Day 1.

Table 5. Template for visioning

Bioeconomy system main theme	Vision BAU (consequence / implication)	Desirable vision	Gap	Gap category
Sub-theme 1	In 2040...			

Bioeconomy system main theme	Vision BAU (consequence / implication)	Desirable vision	Gap	Gap category
Sub-theme 2	In 2040...			
Sub-theme 3	In 2040...			
...	...			

Participants should consider whether BAU vision elements stem from challenges or opportunities and analyse the trajectory of these challenges and opportunities (increasing or decreasing). Desirable vision would be the version of the future where challenges are mitigated, and opportunities are fully realised. The vision should be ambitious and comprehensive, encompassing all the core elements of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. It should aim to:

- ensure food security,
- sustainably manage natural resources,
- reduce dependence on non-renewable resources,
- mitigate and adapt to climate change,
- create jobs,
- maintain European competitiveness (EC 2018).

This approach ensures the vision aligns with the overarching goals and objectives of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy while providing a clear and concise framework for action.

Examples of well formulated desirable visions:

- In 2040, commercialisation of research in the field of crop diversification and rotation reaches the average level of the EU and fully meets national market needs.
- In 2040, a thriving agricultural landscape is characterized by the widespread success of integrated pest and disease management, where demonstrably effective bio-based solutions are the standard.

After formulating a desirable vision, participants identify gaps between the BAU scenario and the desired future. These gaps are categorised as:

- Key policies,
- Key research & innovation,

- Stakeholders,
- New infrastructure,
- Key educational needs,
- Job market,
- Other.

This categorisation ensures comprehensive AP development in subsequent exercises.

Group facilitators can guide groups through brainstorming or encourage individual work followed by a collective discussion to finalise the template.

Examples of gaps with corresponding categories:

- Insufficient technological advancements in bioplastics technology - category: Key Research & Innovation,
- Lack of innovative infrastructure - category: New infrastructure.

6.2.2 Exercise 6: Ensuring alignment and cohesion among desirable vision elements (30 min) - plenary

Next, a group sense-making follows. Groups present their desirable vision elements and identified gaps between the BAU vision and the desirable state. The other groups then provide feedback, noting any discrepancies and working towards an internally consistent vision. Should discrepancies arise regarding the desirable vision elements, a voting process facilitated through Miro boards may be employed. The final outcomes are clearly articulated desirable visions for the sub-themes of the bioeconomy that are not only internally consistent but also aligned with the broader European policy framework for a sustainable and resilient bioeconomy.

6.2.3 Exercise 7: Area-specific strategic planning (3h) - groups

Participants remain in the groups based on the HUB specific themes:

- Agroecology and sustainable yields,
- Biobased materials,
- Bioenergy & new value-added materials,
- Bioeconomy education,
- Food systems,
- Forest value chain,
- Freshwater based bioeconomy.

This exercise is to develop area-specific AP based on the sub-themes' visions and identified gaps. Using a provided template (see Table 6), participants first define specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound strategic objectives.

Table 6. Template for area-specific strategic planning (to be replicated for each sub-theme)

Sub-theme 1	Gap:			
Strategic objective 1:				
Timeline	Key activities	Indicator(s) of success	Funding	Responsibility
Until 2030				
2031-2035				
2036-2040				

Then, for each objective, they outline:

- key activities,
- indicators of success,
- timelines,
- funding,
- responsibilities,

focusing on the 2030 timeframe for the AP while also considering long-term perspectives (2035, 2040). Timeframes can be adjusted to the needs of the specific HUB.

Key activities should encompass:

- *Key policies*, which should be implemented in the state for the bioeconomy vision to become a reality. These can be policies, treaties, blueprints, laws, certification etc. in such fields as: production, digitisation, research, innovation, education, environment, society, technology, cybersecurity, law enforcement, disaster management etc.
- *Key research & innovation*, which would allow the state to leverage on existing and emerging technologies for the bioeconomy vision to become a reality. The main idea is to combine (technological) innovation and application/use in order to streamline the discussion towards applicable research solutions.
- *Stakeholders*, who should be involved, what would be their role and what would be the ways of their engagement at each planning stage for the bioeconomy vision to become a reality. Sample groups of potential stakeholders to consider include: national governments, EU agencies or Directorates-General (DGs), international organisations,

law enforcement agencies, private sector companies, academia and research institutions, civil society & NGOs etc. Sample ways of engagement can be: summits, conferences, multi-stakeholder forums, policy development workshops, foresight workshops, offers of financial incentives, developments of standards and frameworks, joint training programs, joint task forces, public-private partnerships, research grants, technology development and testing, public awareness campaigns, consultations etc. Roles: co-develop strategies, co-develop standards, provide funding, enhance cooperation, co-develop and implement best practices, share knowledge, conduct research, develop educational programs, raise awareness etc.

- *New infrastructure*, which would have to be developed to operationalise new policies, and to use/diffuse the results of new research and innovation.
- *Key educational needs* (societal change, public perception change), required for the bioeconomy vision to become reality.
- *Job market*, where employers not only seek talent to fill existing roles but also actively create new positions and promote innovative solutions to address evolving challenges and potentials.

Indicators of success should be measurable, linked to activities, and clearly demonstrate progress. When considering indicators of success, those developed during the mapping of biomass potential and bioeconomy indicators across the BIOEAST countries in WP3 should be taken into account.

Examples of indicators of success for Agroecology and sustainable yields theme are:

- Annual agricultural biomass production per total land area.
- Agricultural biomass production yields.
- Net exported agricultural biomass per total land area.
- Share of agricultural biomass of total biomass production.
- Rate of soil organic carbon change.
- Water use efficiency.
- Carbon footprint.
- Change in Biodiversity Intactness Index.
- Value of annual agricultural biomass production per utilized agricultural area.
- Gross Value Added (GVA) in agricultural biomass production per utilized agricultural area.

Examples of indicators of success for Biobased materials theme are:

- Bio-material replacing non-renewable resources (substitutes).
- Circular material use rate.

Examples of indicators of success for Food systems theme are:

- Share of conversion into food & feed in domestic biomass valorisation.
- Agricultural biomass production yields.
- Infrastructure for collection and management of agricultural residues and food industry sector residues/by-products.

Examples of indicators of success for Bioenergy & new value-added materials theme are:

- Number of bioenergy plants at national level (Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 6 or higher).
- Bioenergy plants using residual biomass or by-products.
- Number of research projects and process development (TRL 3-5) for bioenergy.
- Bio-material replacing non-renewable resources (substitutes).
- New value chains for bio-based products.
- Number of projects scaling up from pilot to demonstration projects.

Examples of indicators of success for Bioeconomy education theme are:

- Skills demanded by the bioeconomy sector.
- Number of research projects and process development (TRL 3-5) for bioenergy and biorefineries.
- Technology transfer.
- Stakeholder networks that facilitate collaboration among bioeconomy actors.
- Advisory services focalized on rural bioeconomy businesses.

Examples of indicators of success for Forest value chain theme are:

- Annual woody biomass production per total land area.
- Woody biomass production yields.
- Net exported woody biomass per total land area.
- Share of woody biomass of total biomass production.
- Value of annual forestry biomass production per utilized forestry area.
- GVA in woody biomass production per utilized forestry area.
- Infrastructure for collection and management of forestry residues.

Examples of indicators of success for Freshwater-based bioeconomy theme are:

- Annual aquatic biomass production per total water surface area.
- Aquaculture biomass production yields.
- Net exported aquatic biomass per total water surface area.
- Share of aquatic biomass of total biomass production.
- Advisory services focalized on rural bioeconomy businesses.

- Value of annual aquatic biomass production per total water surface area.
- GVA in aquatic biomass production per total water surface area.
- Infrastructure for collection and management of other biomass residues.

However, individual groups have the flexibility to define and utilize their own indicators as needed to complement the existing framework.

The funding section should identify potential funding sources needed for the implementation of projected actions.

The responsibility section should identify the entities responsible for implementation.

The group facilitator guides participants through this process, ensuring that projected actions are feasible with respect to both responsible entities and viable funding options.

Example of activity with all corresponding information:

Table 7. Filled area-specific template with a sub-theme example for Agroecology and sustainable yields theme

Sub-theme 1 Crop diversification and rotation	Gap: Insufficient technological advancements in crop diversification			
Strategic objective 1: Increase the number of joint research projects between universities and businesses in the crop diversification in the given country by 50% within the next ten years.				
Timeline	Key activities	Indicator(s) of success	Funding	Responsibility
Until 2030	Knowledge exchange/ training programmes	total number of participants	National funds	Ministry (depending on country)

6.2.4 Exercise 8: Strategising for the bioeconomy considered holistically (2,5h) - plenary

Each group presents their completed strategising templates, showcasing the detailed AP fragments they developed for their specific theme in the previous exercise. They focus their presentations on strategic objectives and key activities. This allows the participants to:

- Identify synergies to discover opportunities for collaboration and mutual benefit between sectors.

- Ensure consistency to confirm alignment across all sectors.

To facilitate this process, the groups move the objectives and actions designed in the previous task to the common board. For in-person workshops, flip charts can be used. For virtual workshops using Miro, a pre-prepared template is available (Appendix 4). The template is shown in Figure 1.

Strategising for the bioeconomy considered holistically

Figure 1. Template for strategising for the bioeconomy considered holistically

This visual representation helps participants identify linkages and connections across themes.

6.2.5 Summary, feedback and closure

The HUB Coordinator summarises the key outcomes of Day 2, highlighting the desirable vision, and key actions projected for the bioeconomy AP.

The HUB Coordinator thanks participants for their active engagement and contributions and provides a brief overview of the next steps, outlining future-proofing process. If the outcomes are not satisfactory, the HUB Coordinator may ask participants to take part in a post-workshop written consultations to validate the AP for the bioeconomy (on the sub-themes level). This can be done to refine the wording, and the next step would be to conduct a survey for general understanding and reach a consensus on the format of the prepared AP by the HUB Coordinator.

6.3 Outcomes

During the Day 2, the following key outcomes should be achieved:

- **Desirable visions for a bioeconomy.** Outlines the long-term aspirations for a sustainable bioeconomy, addressing its potential challenges and opportunities, and diverging from the BAU approach.
- **Actions for the HUB Themes - Input for the AP.** Participants will develop detailed AP for their themes (on the sub-themes level), including strategic objectives, key activities, timelines, funding sources, and responsibilities. This will result in a comprehensive set of actionable steps that will drive progress towards the desired bioeconomy visions within each specific sub-theme.

Overall, Day 2 will provide detailed actions to be included in the AP. The assumption is that, after the workshop, the HUB Coordinator can populate the last chapter of the AP, which is about projected initiatives. This is the last step of the process within the Three Horizons methodology.

7 Workshop design - Day 3: Future-proofing

7.1 Overall objectives

- Testing the content of AP in the perspective of different possible futures.
- Introducing amendments to AP that make them resistant to potential future disruptions.

7.2 Introduction

The workshop begins with a brief introduction in which the HUB Coordinator explains the basic concepts underlying foresight and scenario analysis (Appendix 5) to the participants. In this

way, participants are introduced to non-linear thinking, which is designed to shake them out of the belief that future events are predictable.

When introducing the concept of foresight, the HUB Coordinator emphasises the importance of understanding the three premises on which considerations about the future are based. These are:

- The future is not predictable. We are therefore forced to consider plausible futures.
- The future is not totally predetermined. There is an infinite number of potential alternative futures, some of which may be more probable than others.
- To some extent, future outcomes can be influenced by our choices in the present. Even though we cannot determine which of the infinite possibilities for a future will eventuate, we can influence the probability of a certain outcome with our choices (both actions and indications) in the present.

7.3 Exercises

7.3.1 Exercise 9: Scenario analysis

Aim

Scenario analysis aims to gain insights into how alternative futures, called scenarios, might influence the subject of analysis, the bioeconomy in the case of the BOOST4BIOEAST project. Scenario analysis usually serves two primary purposes (Volkery & Ribeiro 2009):

- a) To stress-test the subject of analysis, typically consisting in visions, actions and objectives, to check whether they are future-proof. To do this effectively, users of the method must become very familiar with the scenarios and be able to relate them to the issue under analysis. It is important that they consider not only the direct impact of the events described on the subject of analysis but also the phenomena/actions that would be the consequences of such events.
- b) To reframe the users of the method, to make them aware of the boundaries and assumptions they have about the current and future reality, which may influence their ideas and actions. Reframing often leads to higher awareness for decision-making.

Scenario development is usually a lengthy process that may take several months. Therefore, the scenarios will not be developed from scratch. Instead, the HUB Coordinators should rely on scenarios (Košir *et al.* 2021) that had already been developed within BIOEASTsUP project. For the scenarios to be useful in the context of the BOOST4BIOEAST project and its future-proofing activity, the scenarios should exhibit the following characteristics:

- ✓ They should cover a wide range of factors that are relevant to AP development (e.g. geopolitics, economy, environment, technology and society).
- ✓ They should encompass an EU Bioeconomy Strategy for 2040 (a timeline, which relates to AP development).

- ✓ They should be created from an EU perspective so that they would include factors and developments relevant to the EU.
- ✓ None of the scenarios can be disregarded as highly improbable.

Scenarios which meet the above listed criteria and will be included as model scenarios for the future-proofing activity are Reference foresight scenarios: Scenarios on the global standing of the EU in 2040 (Vesnic Alujevic, L. *et al.* 2023). Descriptions of scenarios are in Appendices no. 6, 7, 8 and 9.

Scenario analysis in the BOOST4BIOEAST project aims to gain insights into how alternative futures might influence the subject of analysis: AP of the bioeconomy (Borzacchiello *et al.* 2024; Košir *et al.* 2021).

Flow of work

Participants are familiarized with the outlines of all the long-term future scenarios by the HUB Coordinator. These scenarios are models of the future that help them grapple with its complexity. Participants are then divided into four groups, each assigned one of four scenarios.

In each group, the group facilitator introduces participants to various roles they can embody to better immerse themselves in the scenario being analysed:

- High-ranking official in the Ministry of Agriculture and Food
- University professor leading a team developing new bio-based materials
- Entrepreneur running a start-up company focused on producing biogas
- Manager of a state-owned forest
- Leader of a farmer cooperative
- Urban resident with a strong commitment to environmental sustainability
- Representative of a venture capital fund seeking to invest in innovative bioeconomy start-ups
- Official from the European Commission's DG for Research and Innovation
- Leader of a non-governmental organization advocating for sustainable and ethical bioeconomy development
- Older farmer with a long history of working the land
- Young, tech-savvy entrepreneur interested in exploring innovative farming techniques
- Municipal official
- Engineer working in a company developing new bio-based plastics
- Factory director
- Bank manager
- Inhabitant of the small, rural community

These roles are general descriptions designed to guide individual reflection on the future presented in the scenario. Each participant selects a role and familiarizes themselves with the

scenario (descriptions of scenarios are in Appendices no. 6, 7, 8 and 9), imagining they are actually living in that future.

The group facilitator then presents the group with questions for each participant to consider:

- Who are you? What are you working on?
- What is your most recent success? What are you proud of?
- What's your recent challenge or failure? What are you struggling with?

Participants individually reflect on these questions and then introduce their character to the rest of the group.

If time allows, the following questions can further stimulate discussion:

- What are your biggest concerns and priorities?
- What challenges and opportunities do you face?
- How has technology affected your daily life and work?
- How do you balance economic growth with sustainability concerns? What are the potential risks and benefits?
- What stakeholders do you collaborate with (national, international)? In what way?
- How does the political and legal situation affect your professional activity?

By exploring these questions and embodying their roles, participants deeply immerse themselves in the envisioned future. This immersion prepares them for the next task, where they will critically examine the AP developed during the Three Horizon workshop in relation to the given scenario.

7.3.2 Exercise 10: Future-proofing

Aim

This part of the workshop guides participants through an in-depth analysis of their AP's resilience in the face of different future scenarios.

Flow of work

Participants are divided into four groups, each assigned one of four long-term future scenarios.

Using a provided template (see Table 8) outlining the AP's Strategic Objectives and Actions, each group examines these elements against the predefined future scenario. This analysis challenges them to determine whether each objective and activity remains valid or requires modification for successful implementation in the given scenario.

Participants are then asked to propose modifications to these objectives and activities so that they are still valid in the context of potential future disruptions and uncertainties.

Table 8. Template for future-proofing (to be replicated for each gap)

Strategic objective / Activity		Scenario X	Final modification
Desirable vision of sub-theme		Is the vision ambitious enough? Can it be achieved? Why not?	
Strategic objective1		Is it valid and achievable in the conditions of the scenario? / no changes? / should be modified? additional objectives /actions needed?	
Key Activity 1			
Key Activity 2			
...			

7.3.3 Exercise 11: Report back

A plenary session for all groups is held to present their proposed changes to the AP resulting from future-proofing and to reach consensus among the groups on the final wording.

By discussing proposed adjustments across all four scenarios, participants collaboratively examine and refine (if need be) each strategic element of the AP (e.g. the desired vision, objectives or the key activities to achieve the objectives). Finally, they identify "vulnerable" objectives and activities – those that needed to be modified due to changes or implementation challenges in at least two scenarios. Those objectives and activities are being modified to be more resilient in the face of potential future disruptions and uncertainties. This vulnerability assessment helps prioritise future efforts and ensures the plan's adaptability to uncertain futures.

7.3.4 Summary, feedback, closure

The HUB Coordinator invites participants to reflect on the process and invites them to share some of the lessons learned using the following guiding questions:

- What was the most valuable thing you learned during this workshop?
- What new perspectives or insights did you gain about bioeconomy that you didn't have before?
- How has this workshop influenced your thinking about bioeconomy?

The HUB Coordinator summarises the key outcomes of Day 3 highlighting the key modifications for the bioeconomy AP.

The HUB Coordinator thanks participants for their active engagement and contributions.

7.4 Outcomes

During Day 3, the following key outcome should be achieved:

- Future-proofed actions for the bioeconomy.

Identified vulnerabilities within the AP will be addressed, minimising potential risks and enhancing the overall robustness of the plans. That will result in objectives and actions within the AP that are refined, more resistant and adaptable to potential future disruptions and uncertainties.

8 Conclusion

The action planning process, as described in this document, offers a robust and adaptable framework for shaping the future of bioeconomy in BIOEAST countries. By fostering collaboration, future-oriented thinking and strategic action among stakeholders, it has the potential to drive transformative change in the bioeconomy sector. The APs that emerge from this process are not merely static documents but dynamic blueprints that can guide BIOEAST countries towards a more sustainable, resilient, and prosperous bioeconomy. Furthermore, the flexibility and adaptability of the methodology ensures that it can be tailored to the specific context and needs of each BIOEAST country, thereby maximising its effectiveness and impact. By promoting a holistic and participatory approach to bioeconomy development, the action planning process can pave the way for a more sustainable and prosperous future for the BIOEAST macro-region.

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10 Appendices

Appendix 1. [Standardised template](#)

Appendix 2. [Pre-workshop survey template](#)

Appendix 3. [Action Plan - reporting template](#)

Appendix 4. Miro board template: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVLwj3Ozg=/>

Appendix 5. Recording with Introduction to the workshop

Appendix 6. [Future-proofing. Scenario 1 description](#)

Appendix 7. [Future-proofing. Scenario 2 description](#)

Appendix 8. [Future-proofing. Scenario 3 description](#)

Appendix 9. [Future-proofing. Scenario 4 description](#)

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